

MA Degree Thesis by Examination

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Modeling Human-Elephant Interaction and Conflict Amidst Climate Change and Development Pressures

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Abstract:

This study examines human-elephant interactions and conflicts amid climate change and development pressures, focusing on the African Elephant (*Loxodonta africana*). Using Agent-Based Modeling (ABM) in NetLogo, the research explores how these factors impact elephant behavior and conservation strategies. The study draws on the Land-Sparing vs. Land-Sharing Debate, assessing the effects of separating or integrating human and wildlife activities. It also utilizes Climate Change Adaptation and Resilience Theory to understand the adaptive capacity of human and wildlife populations. The findings indicate that land-sharing scenarios lead to higher conflict rates and poaching, while land-sparing scenarios reduce direct conflicts but increase poaching at protected area boundaries. Development and climate pressures exacerbate resource scarcity, resulting in heightened conflicts, particularly in shared land scenarios. High energy costs for elephants correlate with increased mortality, underscoring the critical need for resource management. The research concludes that a combination of land-sparing and land-sharing, along with adaptive management strategies, can help mitigate conflicts and promote coexistence. These insights are crucial for developing effective conservation policies that consider ecological and socio-economic factors, ensuring sustainable coexistence between humans and elephants in changing environments.

Introduction:

Human-wildlife conflict (HWC) presents a pressing challenge that leads to detrimental outcomes such as biodiversity loss, zoonotic disease transmission, mental stress, physical injury, property damage, and agricultural yield reduction (Abrahms, 2021). Despite decades of conservation efforts, HWC remains a significant issue globally, exacerbated by climate change and development. This phenomenon leads to increased incidence of wildfires, forest health decline, and altered distribution patterns of key wildlife species (Konig et al., 2021), like the African Elephant (*Loxodonta Africana*). Furthermore, rapid land use expansion for residential, industrial, and agricultural purposes further worsens the problem through wildlife habitat fragmentation (Cuesta & Michalski, 2022).

In the global biodiversity conservation efforts, the human-elephant systems present a complex challenge due to elephants' roles in sustaining ecosystem services, their unique composition, and their fragile lifecycle and reproduction cycle. Their size and trunk make them an obvious threat to people and make them vulnerable to poachers. Elephants are a keystone species vital to African rainforest biodiversity and carbon storage (WWF, 2018). Internationally renowned and classified as endangered or critically endangered, they are often the focus of conservation campaigns (Barua, 2014). However, their large dietary needs often lead to intense resource competition with humans, manifesting starkly as conflicts around crops and water, and even attacks on livestock as observed in Nigeria, Kenya, and other tropical regions.

Climate and development pressures are further worsening these scenarios. Recent studies show that climate change has emerged as a major concern, surpassing poaching. Elephants' wide-ranging behavior, spending over 70% of their time outside protected areas, increasingly competes for space and resources with growing human populations and changing land-use patterns (Thouless et al., 2016). Notably, elephants can cause severe damage to small-holder crops, leading to retaliatory actions from farmers, jeopardizing long-term conservation efforts (Mijeje et al., 2013). Spatially, crop-raiding tends to occur more frequently closer to forest edges and protected areas, away from roads, and in areas of low human density.

Achieving human-wildlife coexistence, particularly with elephants, necessitates integrating nuanced approaches like Agent-Based Modeling (ABM) into predictive and impactful solutions. Hence, this writeup aims to show how I engage with ABM using NetLogo to attempt to proffer solutions to key conservation questions about human-elephant conflicts (HEC). For a good pictorial summary of my explanation, figure 1 succinctly summarizes my intent with the below ABM model.

Figure 1: Conceptual diagram of Human wildlife interactions and conflicts (Adapted from Andrew Bell)

Research Questions:

1. How do changes in climate patterns influence the movement and behavior of elephants, leading to variations in the frequency and intensity of HEC incidents?
2. How do land-sharing and land-sparing strategies affect elephant populations and human livelihoods?

Key Questions for the Model:

1. What are people's needs and how are they met?
2. What are elephants' needs and how are they met?
3. What happens when elephants and humans interact?
4. How do barriers (land sparing) or no barriers (land sharing) impact the ability to meet these needs?
5. How do different climate scenarios impact, individually or together with various policies (with/without barriers), the ability to meet the needs of humans and elephants?

The Model is Heavily Based on Key Debates and Frameworks in Biodiversity

Conservation:

1. Land-Sparing vs. Land-Sharing Debate (Phalan et al., 2011; Fischer et al., 2008)

This concept from conservation biology discusses two contrasting strategies for biodiversity conservation:

- Land Sparing: Separating land for human use and conservation areas to minimize human-wildlife conflicts and maximize habitat protection.
- Land Sharing: Integrating conservation and human activities on the same land to promote coexistence and sustainable use of resources.

Assumptions:

- Land sparing may lead to higher protection for wildlife but could limit human access to resources and increase human-wildlife conflict at boundaries.
- Land sharing promotes coexistence but may result in lower conservation effectiveness and higher direct interactions between humans and wildlife.

2. Climate Change Adaptation and Resilience Theory (Adger et al., 2009; Folke et al., 2009): This theory focuses on how systems (human or ecological) can adjust to climate change, mitigate potential damage, exploit opportunities, or cope with consequences. It includes concepts of vulnerability, adaptive capacity, and resilience.

Assumptions:

- Climate change alters resource availability and distribution, affecting both human livelihoods and wildlife behaviors.
- Adaptive capacity varies among human communities and wildlife populations, influencing their ability to cope with climate-induced changes.
- Building resilience involves enhancing the capacity of both humans and wildlife to adapt to changing conditions.

Summary of My ABM Code

The ABM code initializes and manages a simulation tracking interactions between humans and elephants, with several global variables to monitor aspects like time, economic status thresholds, resource levels, and development effects. It defines patch properties and two breeds, humans and elephants, each with attributes like age, location, economic status, and memory of resource levels. The setup function initializes patches, humans, and elephants, setting their initial conditions and locations. The main execution loop, go, updates the simulation by switching seasons, updating economic statuses, moving agents, and simulating behaviors and interactions, ultimately aiming to study the impact of land-sharing and land-sparing strategies and climate change on human-elephant interaction.

Behavior and Decision-making

- **Human Behavior:** This is movement (farm expansion mechanism) is based on human economic status within the simulation. High-economic-status humans expand without restriction if land sparing is not in effect; otherwise, they move with restrictions. Middle-economic-status humans attempt to move every half of the expansion time, with the same condition regarding land sparing. Low-economic-status humans attempt to move every full expansion time, again considering land sparing. Movement involves identifying target patches first in village areas and, if unavailable, in protected areas, with higher resource

levels and within a specified distance. If a suitable patch is found, the human occupies it, updates memory attributes, and performs farming. The switch-season function toggles between wet and dry seasons based on the defined number of wet months per year.

There are also functions to update the economic status of humans, manage their farming activities, and handle their overall behavior. The update-economic-status function resets counts for different economic status categories and updates each human's status based on their average resource level and disposable money. The farm function allows humans to either harvest resources from their occupied patches during the dry season if resource levels are sufficient or increase resource levels otherwise. The harvest function calculates the number of resources a human can harvest without depleting the patch below a minimum threshold, adds the gain to the human's money, and normalizes money distribution to ensure a capped average. The human-behavior function checks for aging or starvation, tracking deaths and removing humans from the simulation as necessary.

- **Elephant Behavior:** The movement and foraging behaviors of elephants within the simulation directs them to seek patches with sufficient resources in protected or shared areas, moving them there if the patches are not already occupied by other elephants. If no suitable patches are found, elephants will move towards village edges. Movement depletes the elephants' energy, which they replenish through the forage function by consuming available resources on their current patch. The elephant-behavior function integrates these actions, allowing elephants to move, forage, and check for aging or starvation, removing them from the simulation if necessary.
- **The Interactions:** The code manages the interactions within the simulation, focusing on resource updates and human-elephant conflict dynamics. The update-resources function adjusts patch resource levels based on climate change effects, seasonal variations, and development impacts, ensuring resource levels remain within bounds. The function also calculates and normalizes total and average resource levels if necessary. The update-conflict function addresses human and elephant interactions, with conflicts arising from proximity and resource scarcity. Humans may engage in poaching when their resource

levels are low, while elephants resort to crop-raiding when their energy levels are insufficient. Non-conflict interactions occur when resource levels and energy are adequate.

Additionally, the simulation includes age updates and death age tracking for both humans and elephants. The add-age function increases the age of all agents every 12 ticks, while the update-mean-death-ages function calculates and updates the mean death ages. The add-resource function computes the mean resource levels for different land types and sums them to obtain a total resource value, providing a comprehensive overview of the resource distribution across the simulation landscape. These interactions collectively simulate the complex dynamics of human-elephant coexistence, factoring in economic status, resource availability, and the impacts of climate change and development.

Visualization:

Utilize NetLogo's visualization tools to depict resource levels, agent movements, and conflict incidents over time for analysis and communication.

Method Explanation:

This experiment was designed to evaluate the impact of various factors on human-elephant interactions, with each tick representing one month (and ran all for 2 years). The key outcomes measured include:

Mean resource level of protected patches

Mean resource level of shared patches

Mean resource level of village patches

Mean human death age

Mean elephant death age

Count of humans with middle income

Count of humans with high income

Count of humans with low income

Total interactions

Elephant deaths

Human deaths

Poaching incidents

Total crop raiding

The simulation tests different scenarios where land sparing, development, and climate change are either true or false, while keeping other parameters constant. This approach allows for a controlled examination of how each factor influences the dynamics of human-elephant coexistence and resource management.

Result:

1. A Normal scenario land sharing scenario where there is no climate nor development pressures.

2. A normal land sparing scenario when there is no climate nor development pressure

3. Land Sharing with Development and Climate Pressures

4. Land sparing with Development and Climate scenarios

Other parameters:

5a. Low energy movement cost!

ticks: 24

5b. High energy movement cost

6a. With more resources: less conflict

6b. Lower resources, more conflict

7a. Low Starvation threshold affect humans

7b. High Starvation threshold affect humans

Explanation:

1. Normal Land Sharing Scenario without Climate or Development Pressures: In this scenario, resource levels remained high, and no conflicts were recorded. People lived economically well, but the few elephant deaths occurred at relatively low ages. The picture shows people setting up tents even within the protected zones.
2. Normal Land Sparing Scenario without Climate or Development Pressures: With land sparing, people were restricted from entering protected zones, as shown in the picture. Despite high resource levels, there were more poaching activities and conflict incidents.
3. Land Sharing with Development and Climate Pressures: Resource availability was significantly impacted, leading to depletion. Out of an initial count of 33 elephants, 28 died due to lack of resources, alongside 3 human deaths. Crop raiding increased, and most interactions (74) led to conflicts (50). No poaching was observed, and there were many low-income farmers.
4. Land Sparing with Development and Climate Pressures: Overall conflict was lower, but resources were still depleted due to environmental pressures. Poaching activities increased, with people becoming more aggressive towards elephants and engaging in more poaching.
5. Elephant Energy Depletion Costs: Lower energy depletion costs resulted in fewer elephant deaths, with only 2 deaths from resource scarcity in the low-energy scenario. Conversely, higher energy costs led to the death of all 33 elephants.
6. Resource Availability and Conflict: Higher resource levels resulted in fewer conflicts. With over 201 interactions, no conflicts occurred when resources were abundant. In contrast, with lower resource inputs, there were over 73 conflicts under the same conditions.
7. Starvation Threshold and Human Deaths: The starvation threshold significantly affected human death ages. A higher starvation threshold resulted in a lower mean age of death and more deaths, while a lower threshold led to a higher mean age of death and fewer deaths. This is because the condition to die was either starvation or age, impacting the overall mortality rate.

Conclusion and Next Steps:

The simulation provides valuable insights into how various factors uniquely influence human-elephant interactions. It highlights complex dynamics that are not always intuitively obvious, demonstrating the importance of modeling in understanding these interactions.

Next Steps:

- Refine Model Assumptions: Enhance the realism of the model by refining its assumptions to ensure that the interactions of interest are accurately represented.
- Focus on Specific Questions: Ensure the model addresses specific questions of concern, thereby providing more targeted and relevant insights.
- Develop a Mini Game Model: Create an interactive mini game model to help inform farmers' decisions. This tool can simulate different conditions, policy changes, seasons, and conflicts, improving our understanding of human reactions and finetuning our assumptions for a comprehensive model that can facilitate better decision-making and policy development for human-elephant coexistence.

Through these steps, the model can become a more effective tool for predicting outcomes and informing strategies to mitigate human-elephant conflicts, thereby promoting sustainable coexistence.

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